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MODELLING AEROSOL EFFECTS ON CLIMATE: FROM
ORGANIC VOLATILES TO CLOUD INTERACTIONS AND
RADIATIVE FORCING

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Abstract

Aerosols play a critical role in Earth's climate by influencing cloud formation, atmospheric chemistry, and radiative balance. However, aerosol-cloud and aerosol-radiation interactions remain major sources of uncertainty, affecting both radiative forcing estimates and future climate projections. A significant fraction of atmospheric aerosols originates from secondary organic aerosol (SOA), which forms through the oxidation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Modelling SOA is challenging due to the multitude of oxidation products involved, which exhibit a wide range of volatilities that influence their gas-particle partitioning. Moreover, the volatilities of these oxidation products remain highly uncertain, making it difficult to model SOA formation and its impact on climate. In addition to SOA, primary aerosols from forest wood use contribute to atmospheric composition and climate, with their impact depending on how harvested wood is utilized. Key emissions from forest wood use, including black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), and sulphur dioxide (SO₂), contribute to radiative forcing and influence climate processes. Furthermore, the relationship between Cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and cloud droplet number concentration (CDNC) is not straightforward, as it depends on multiple atmospheric factors beyond CCN alone. It is therefore essential to understand these interconnected processes, which are critical for improving the aerosol representation in climate models and reducing uncertainties in aerosol radiative forcing estimates.

This thesis investigates three key aspects of aerosol-climate interactions by integrating process-level modelling, global climate model simulations, satellite observations, and statistical analysis. First, we examine how the volatilities of SOA precursors influence particle growth to CCN sizes and radiative effects. This is done using the Volatility Basis Set (VBS) framework in both process-scale and global-scale models. The VBS approach represents organic compounds by grouping them into discrete volatility bins, improving the modelling of their role in the atmosphere. Second, we assess the impact of alternate forest biomass use in Finland on aerosol emissions and radiative forcing. Third, we investigate the limitations of traditional regression methods in estimating the

correlation between CCN and CDNC and propose a machine-learning based approach to improve our understanding on aerosol-cloud interactions.

To address uncertainties in the volatility of VOC oxidation products, we performed global climate model simulations to evaluate how different volatility assumptions influence modelled aerosol effects on climate. Our results indicate that a ten-fold decrease in the assumed volatility increases SOA burden by 13 %, whereas, an increase in volatility reduces it by 9 %. This change exerts a moderate effect on CCN concentrations, with a decrease of 3 % for increased volatility and an increase of 2 % for reduced volatility relative to the original volatility. Comparing the binning of VBS to three and nine volatility classes reveals that the choice of the resolution of volatility bins substantially influences CCN estimates. Our study on radiative forcing from different wood use scenarios shows that while instantaneous radiative forcing (IRF_{ARI}) remains relatively small, aerosol-induced effective radiative forcing (ERF) can be significant due to changes in the allocation of additional wood harvest. The net ERF over Finland is $+0.13 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ for increased pulpwood harvest, whereas for increased energy biomass combustion in small-scale boilers, it reaches -0.90 W m^{-2} . Finally, we investigated the correlation between CCN and CDNC using traditional least square methods such as ordinary least squares in its two-dimensional form (OLS) and bivariate least squares (BLS). We found that while BLS accounts for uncertainties in both axes, it often produces unphysical slope estimates. Both methods are inherently bivariate and fail to consider additional confounding variables. These limitations underscore the need for a more comprehensive approach that accounts for key atmospheric factors to better quantify aerosol-cloud interactions. We propose the use of a more comprehensive approach, such as machine learning, to improve CCN-CDNC slope estimates.

Overall, this thesis underscores the persistent uncertainties in aerosol-cloud interactions and emphasizes the need for improved representation of organic aerosols in global-scale models. It highlights the importance of employing appropriate statistical methods and refining aerosol-cloud-radiation assessments to improve our understanding of their climatic impacts.

Keywords: Modelling, volatility, SOA, clouds, satellite, machine-learning, cloud parcel model, updraft velocity, forest biomass, emissions

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List of publications

This thesis consists of an introductory review, followed by three research articles. In the introductory part, the papers are cited according to their roman numerals. **Paper I and Paper II** are reproduced under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License. **Paper III** is included with permission from the publisher and is currently under review.

- I. Irfan, M.**, Kühn, T., Yli-Juuti, T., Laakso, A., Holopainen, E., Worsnop, D. R., Virtanen, A., & Kokkola, H. (2024). A model study investigating the sensitivity of aerosol forcing to the volatilities of semi-volatile organic compounds. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, *24*(14), 8489–8506. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-8489-2024>
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1 Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols, composed of microscopic solid or liquid particles suspended in the air, range in sizes from a few nanometers to tens of micrometers (Hinds, 1999). Although their concentration in the atmosphere is relatively low, aerosols are among the most dynamic and complex components of the Earth's climate system (Albrecht, 1989). These particles undergo rapid chemical transformations that affect their composition, optical properties, and interactions with clouds and radiation (Putaud et al., 2010). Aerosols play a critical role in regulating the Earth's energy balance, by absorbing or reflecting solar radiation (Twomey, 1977). They also act as seeds necessary for cloud formation, thereby influencing cloud properties and precipitation patterns (Albrecht, 1989). Beyond their climatic effects, aerosols significantly influence the air quality and human health, primarily by degrading air quality, with fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) being strongly linked to various respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Pope III & Dockery, 2006). This makes aerosols a key focus in climate science, air quality, and public health research.

Aerosols originate from both natural and anthropogenic sources. They are classified as either primary or secondary based on how they form (Hallquist et al., 2009). Primary aerosols enter the atmosphere directly from natural sources such as volcanic eruptions, desert dust, sea spray, and wildfires (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). Human activities also contribute to primary aerosol emissions, especially through fossil fuel combustion, industrial processes, and biomass burning. Secondary aerosols, however, do not enter the atmosphere directly. Rather, they form within the atmosphere through the condensation of organic or inorganic vapours. These vapours can either nucleate into new particles or condense onto existing particles. The distinction between primary and secondary particles is quite complex, as atmospheric particles can undergo various processes, such as chemical transformations, which complicate the categorization of aerosols (Robinson et al., 2007). This highlights the dynamic and evolving nature of atmospheric aerosols.

Among the different components of atmospheric aerosols, organic aerosol (OA) is particularly important due to its abundance and intricate atmospheric behaviour (Jimenez et al., 2009). OA is broadly classified as either primary or secondary, based on its source and formation mechanism. Primary organic aerosol (POA) is directly emitted from sources such as biomass burning, fossil fuel combustion, vegetation, and cooking

activities (Spracklen et al., 2011). In contrast, secondary organic aerosol (SOA) is formed through the oxidation of VOCs, a process characterized by complex chemical pathways. These reactions produce a wide range of oxidation products with volatilities significantly lower than those of their parent compounds. These lower volatility products may condense on existing particles or form new particles, thus leading to the formation of SOA. VOCs that contribute to SOA formation can be either natural or anthropogenic in origin. Biogenic VOCs, including isoprene, monoterpenes, and sesquiterpenes, come primarily from vegetation and account for most of global SOA production (Guenther et al., 2012). Anthropogenic VOCs, such as aromatic hydrocarbons from traffic emissions, also play a significant role in SOA formation, particularly in polluted urban areas (Ziemann & Atkinson, 2012).

Once released into the atmosphere, both primary and secondary aerosols undergo a variety of physical and chemical processes that significantly influence their atmospheric lifetime and properties (Jacobson, 2005a). These processes, which include coagulation, condensation, evaporation, and removal, affect both the size and chemical composition of aerosols. Newly formed particles can rapidly grow as they accumulate mass from condensing vapors, or they may undergo chemical changes that alter their structure (Zhang et al., 2012). These processes contribute to the dynamic behavior of aerosols in the atmosphere and their ability to influence air quality and climate (Pandis et al., 1995).

Aerosols interact with climate through two key mechanisms: aerosol-radiation interactions (ARI) and aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI) (Haywood & Boucher, 2000). ARI influences Earth's energy balance through the direct scattering or absorption of solar radiation. Depending on their chemical composition, some aerosols such as sulfates, scatter solar radiation back to space, leading to a cooling effect, while others like black carbon absorb radiation, warming the atmosphere (Allen & Sherwood, 2011; Buseck & Pósfai, 1999). ACI further complicates the aerosol effects on climate by modulating cloud properties and precipitation patterns. Acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), aerosols influence cloud droplet number concentration (CDNC), which in turn affects cloud reflectivity, and precipitation efficiency. More aerosols generally lead to a larger number of smaller cloud droplets, increasing the cloud albedo and the cooling effect, known as the Twomey effect (Twomey, 1977). However, these smaller droplets can also reduce rainfall, extend cloud lifetimes, and alter atmospheric circulation pattern (Albrecht, 1989). Under dry atmospheric conditions, smaller droplets can instead

reduce cloud lifetime by enhancing evaporation, leading to faster cloud dissipation (Ackerman et al., 2004; Toll et al., 2019). Together, these myriad effects highlight the multifaceted role of aerosols in controlling Earth’s energy balance.

OA, particularly SOA, plays a crucial role in shaping the Earth’s climate (Petäjä et al., 2022; Scott et al., 2014; Yli-Juuti et al., 2021). SOA affects the radiative balance by scattering solar radiation and modifying cloud properties (Kanakidou et al., 2005). Beyond climate effects, OA forms a major constituent of fine particulate matter, which presents considerable health risks to humans and ecosystems (Zhang et al., 2015). However, the atmospheric lifecycle of SOA is highly complex, primarily due to their formation mechanisms, which involve oxidation reactions of VOCs in the atmosphere (Shrivastava et al., 2013). This process results in the formation of a multitude of oxidation products with a broad spectrum of volatilities. The volatility of these oxygenated compounds determines their partitioning between the gas and particle phases. This gas-particle partitioning directly affects the growth and evolution of SOA, and their overall impact on climate (Hodzic et al., 2016).

To better represent these complex processes in climate models, various frameworks have been developed, including the Volatility Basis Set (VBS), which groups organic compounds based on their volatility (Donahue et al., 2006). One key variable in this framework is C_{sat} , the saturation vapour concentration. C_{sat} serves as an indicator of volatility, where higher C_{sat} values correspond to more volatile compounds that remain in the gas phase, while lower C_{sat} values indicate lower volatility, leading to condensation onto aerosols. Since volatility governs gas-particle partitioning, inaccuracies in its estimation can subsequently influence SOA formation, CCN concentration, and radiative effects. These uncertainties can then lead to inaccuracies in aerosol concentrations and their climate effects predicted by climate models (Shrivastava et al., 2011). Hence, it is essential to quantify the effects of different volatility distributions of organic compounds in a global model in order to improve model accuracy and refine our understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions. Specifically, this includes impacts on SOA formation, CCN concentration, CDNC, and radiative effects.

Another main source of aerosols is biomass use, which releases both warming aerosols like black carbon and cooling aerosols like organic carbon (Jacobson, 2014). The growing reliance of forest biomass for energy and industrial applications in several countries (IEA Bioenergy, 2025) raises the question of what this practice means for the climate. Aerosol emissions from biomass combustion are strongly dependent on the scale and

the technology used in combustion. For example, small-scale combustion appliances typically emit more carbonaceous aerosol than larger, more combustion-efficient systems (Bond et al., 2004). These emissions have the potential to influence climate, primarily through ARI and ACI and lead to complex effects on radiative balance. Hence, it is necessary to assess aerosol emissions across different wood use scenarios and their radiative effects (Kalliokoski et al., 2020). Such studies are particularly important for regions such as Finland, where the energy products depend significantly on forest biomass (Hurmekoski et al., 2020). Hence, a deeper understanding of these processes will assist in ensuring sustainable biomass utilization strategies and to guarantee that the climate and environmental goals are met while optimizing the use of this key resource.

Although, it is well established that aerosols act as CCN, affecting CDNC and cloud properties, significant uncertainties persist in accurately quantifying this relationship, particularly between CCN and CDNC. Understanding this relationship is crucial because it directly affects aerosol radiative forcing estimates, which play a key role in climate modelling and projections (Quaas et al., 2006). A key metric for characterizing this relationship is cloud susceptibility, which quantifies how sensitive CDNC is to changes in aerosol concentration. However, accurately estimating susceptibilities remains challenging due to extensive heterogeneities in cloud properties, processes occurring during cloud lifetime, and observational uncertainties. For example, the relationship between aerosols and clouds exhibits significant variability and depends on multiple factors, such as aerosol size distribution and meteorological conditions (Fan et al., 2016; Fanourgakis et al., 2019). This makes it difficult to determine the specific impact of aerosols on cloud properties. The estimation of ACI from satellite data introduces an additional layer of complexity (Gryspeerd et al., 2022). Although satellite observations provide extensive spatial coverage and continuous monitoring, they face challenges in accurately capturing fine-scale microphysical processes occurring within clouds due to retrieval uncertainties and associated assumptions (Quaas et al., 2006). A single satellite snapshot often represents a mix of atmospheric conditions, cloud types, and aerosol properties, making it challenging to isolate aerosol effects from confounding factors like cloud dynamics and background meteorology. Furthermore, the retrieval of key variables, such as CCN and CDNC, involves inherent uncertainties due to indirect estimation methods (Quaas et al., 2006).

These challenges necessitate the use of robust statistical approaches to reduce the

effects of variability and bias in satellite observations. Traditional approaches such as two-dimensional ordinary least squares (OLS) regression have been widely used to capture the relationship between CCN and CDNC. However, OLS regression struggles to account for the complex interactions between these variables, primarily due to uncertainties in both the x and y directions (Pitkänen et al., 2016). This limitation underscores the need for more advanced statistical approaches to improve the accuracy of aerosol-cloud interaction estimates. Machine learning and advanced statistical techniques have emerged as promising tools to overcome these challenges (Gao et al., 2020; Miinalainen et al., 2021). By integrating satellite observations with modelled data, these methods offer the potential to more effectively isolate the effects of aerosols on clouds and refine our understanding of ACI.

Given the critical challenges in aerosol-cloud interactions, this thesis addresses three key aspects of aerosol-climate interactions:

- Investigating the sensitivity of modelled SOA mass, CCN concentrations, and radiative effects to the volatilities of organic compounds (**Paper I**).
- Quantifying radiative forcing from aerosols under different wood-use scenarios over Finland, focusing on emissions, including OC, BC and SO₂ (**Paper II**).
- Evaluating the effectiveness of traditional regression methods in isolating aerosol effects on cloud droplet number concentration and proposing a machine learning approach for improved susceptibility estimates (**Paper III**).

2 Foundations of Aerosol-Climate Interactions

2.1 Aerosol Processes

Atmospheric aerosols undergo a complex series of physical and chemical processes that define their lifecycle, from formation to removal. These processes determine aerosol size, composition, and interactions with radiation and clouds, making them central to atmospheric chemistry and climate studies. This section provides an overview of the mechanisms governing aerosol evolution and their broader significance in atmospheric behaviour.

Atmospheric aerosols are generally classified into four size modes, each associated with distinct formation mechanisms and atmospheric behaviours as shown in Figure 1. Nucleation-mode particles (1–25 nm) are newly formed through gas-phase nucleation and must grow rapidly via condensation to avoid being lost through coagulation with larger particles (Kulmala et al., 2001). In addition to atmospheric nucleation, nucleation-mode particles can also originate from primary sources, such as combustion emissions, particularly traffic (Rönkkö & Timonen, 2019). Aitken-mode particles (25–100 nm) result from the growth of nucleation-mode particles but can also be emitted directly from combustion sources, such as vehicle exhaust and biomass burning. These particles serve as a transitional phase before further growth through condensation or coagulation. Accumulation-mode particles (100–1000 nm) form primarily from the condensation of low-volatility compounds, coagulation of smaller particles, and chemical processing within clouds (Zhou et al., 2020). They play a dominant role in aerosol optical properties, cloud interactions, and long-range transport due to their relatively long atmospheric lifetimes (Kerminen & Wexler, 1995; Paasonen et al., 2018). Coarse-mode particles ($>1 \mu\text{m}$) originate mainly from mechanical processes, such as sea spray generation, dust formation, and biological emissions (Eck et al., 2010). These particles have shorter atmospheric lifetimes as they are efficiently removed by gravitational settling and wet deposition (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016).

Aerosol formation begins with nucleation, where clusters of gas-phase molecules aggregate into more stable particles. This occurs when the concentration of low-volatility gases, such as sulfuric acid or highly oxidized organic compounds, exceeds their saturation point. Nucleation can be either homogeneous, involving pure molecular clus-

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a multi-modal aerosol particle size distribution

tering, or heterogeneous, where pre-existing surfaces such as ions or other particles act as nucleation sites (Kulmala et al., 2013). As nucleated particles evolve, condensation becomes the dominant growth mechanism, where gas-phase molecules deposit onto the surface of existing particles, increasing their size. Low-volatility compounds contribute significantly to this process (Zhang et al., 2012). However, this process is inherently dynamic. As the atmosphere dilutes or temperature increases, some of these condensed compounds may evaporate back into the gas phase, thereby reducing the mass of particles (Pandis et al., 1995). This shift between phases is governed by gas-particle partitioning, a dynamic equilibrium that influences how much of a compound remains in the gas phase versus the particle phase (Kroll & Seinfeld, 2008). This partitioning process is especially important for secondary aerosol formation, as many of the oxidation products of VOCs involved in SOA formation fall into a volatility range where they frequently shift between phases.

Aerosol particles also undergo coagulation, a process in which particles collide and merge, leading to the formation of fewer but larger particles (Jacobson, 2005b). This process is particularly effective for nucleation- and Aitken-mode particles in high-concentration environments, such as urban areas, where frequent particle collisions accelerate their removal from the ultra-fine population (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016).

The size and composition of aerosol particles also play a crucial role in their growth and atmospheric behavior. Aerosol growth involves several mechanisms, including

condensation and coagulation. Particle size is one of the key factors influencing the rate at which these processes occur (Paasonen et al., 2018). For instance, nucleation-mode particles, which grow readily through condensation to avoid being lost via coagulation with larger particles, transition to the Aitken and accumulation-mode particles. These larger particles are more efficient at activating into cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) sizes (Kulmala et al., 2013). The composition of aerosol particles significantly affects their behavior in the atmosphere (Pöschl, 2005). For example, particles composed of sulfuric acid are highly hygroscopic, meaning they attract water vapor, leading to particle growth in humid conditions. This can make them an important component of CCN, playing a critical role in cloud formation and influencing cloud albedo.

Aerosols are eventually removed from the atmosphere, mainly through wet deposition and dry deposition. These removal processes dictate the atmospheric lifetime and regional distribution of aerosols. Wet deposition is the dominant removal process, where aerosols are scavenged by cloud droplets and removed through precipitation (Croft et al., 2010). In contrast, dry deposition occurs when aerosols settle onto surfaces due to gravitational settling or are adsorbed by vegetation, soil, or water surfaces (Farmer et al., 2021). Coarse-mode particles, due to their larger size, are primarily removed by dry deposition, while smaller particles can remain airborne for longer periods, allowing for long-range transport (Jung et al., 2002). The efficiency of these removal mechanisms depends on particle size, shape, and environmental conditions (McMurry, 2000).

2.2 Organic Aerosols

OA constitutes a major component of atmospheric aerosols and play a critical role in air quality, cloud microphysics, and climate forcing (Hallquist et al., 2009). Organic compounds exist in both the gas and particle phases, with their behaviour largely dictated by their chemical properties, primarily volatility (Bilde et al., 2015). Volatility is a key property that determines whether an organic compound remains in the gas phase or condenses into the particle phase, which plays a central role in the formation, evolution, and atmospheric lifetime of SOA.

The formation of SOA begins with the oxidation of VOCs, which produces a wide array of semi- and low-volatility organic compounds that can condense onto pre-existing aerosols or nucleate to form new particles (Hallquist et al., 2009). This gas-to-particle transition, governed by volatility, is quantified by the saturation vapour pressure (P_{sat}),

which represents the equilibrium pressure of a compound’s vapour above its condensed phase (Donahue et al., 2012). The temperature dependence of P_{sat} follows the Clausius-Clapeyron equation:

$$\ln P_{\text{sat}} = \ln P_{\text{ref}} - \frac{\Delta H_{\text{vap}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_{vap} is the enthalpy of vaporization (Jmol^{-1}), R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), T is the temperature (K), and P_{ref} is the reference vapour pressure at the reference temperature T_{ref} . ΔH_{vap} , accounting for temperature dependence, is given by:

$$\Delta H_{\text{vap}} = \Delta H_{T_{\text{vap}}} + T_{\text{vap}} \left[(C_{P,\text{gas}} - C_{P,\text{liquid}}) \ln \left(\frac{T}{T_{\text{vap}}} \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta H_{T_{\text{vap}}}$ is the enthalpy of vaporization at the vaporization temperature T_{vap} (Jmol^{-1}), T_{vap} is the temperature at which the phase transition occurs at a given pressure (K), and $C_{P,\text{gas}}$ and $C_{P,\text{liquid}}$ are the constant-pressure heat capacities of the gas and liquid phases ($\text{Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), respectively.

Equation 1 highlights that P_{sat} decreases exponentially with temperature, favouring condensation under cooler conditions. In atmospheric studies, it is often more practical to use the saturation vapour concentration (C_{sat}), which relates P_{sat} to the compound’s molecular properties and environmental conditions:

$$C_{\text{sat}} = \frac{P_{\text{sat}}M}{RT} \quad (3)$$

where C_{sat} is the saturation vapour concentration (μgm^{-3}) and M is the molar mass of the compound (kgmol^{-1}). The volatility classification of organic compounds depend on their C_{sat} values. For example, compounds with $C_{\text{sat}} < 3 \times 10^{-5} \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ are classified as extremely low-volatility organic compounds (ELVOCs) (Bianchi et al., 2019). These compounds condense almost irreversibly onto any pre-existing cluster and contribute to new particle formation. Low-volatility organic compounds (LVOCs), with C_{sat} values between 3×10^{-3} and $0.3 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ condense readily onto any sufficiently large particles. Semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs), with C_{sat} values ranging from 0.3 to 300

μgm^{-3} , which exist in both gas and particle phases. Intermediate-volatile organic compounds (IVOCs), with C_{sat} values between 300 and $3 \times 10^6 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, exist predominantly in the gas phase under ambient conditions (Schervish & Donahue, 2020).

Organic compounds undergo continuous transformations through oxidation reactions by oxidants such as OH, O₃, and NO₃. When organic compounds react with these oxidants, they undergo transformations that alter their molecular structure and properties (Ng et al., 2017). Some reactions lead to the addition of functional groups, increasing molecular weight and polarity, reducing volatility. Others cause molecular fragmentation, which generally leads to lower molecular weight and increased volatility. However, SOA formation is not limited to a single oxidation step. Rather, the oxidation of a single VOC precursor generates a diverse array of low- and semi-volatile organic compounds, each capable of undergoing further oxidation reactions (Donahue et al., 2012). These atmospheric oxidation processes generally lead to lower organic volatility, enhancing their tendency to condense into the particle phase and increasing SOA mass. These transformations and associated volatility changes pose challenges for accurately measuring volatilities (Donahue et al., 2011; Karnezi et al., 2014). This introduces uncertainties that can propagate into climate models, potentially leading to errors in modelled SOA formation and its atmospheric impacts (Shrivastava et al., 2013).

Addressing these uncertainties is, hence, crucial for improving predictions of SOA effects on air quality, cloud formation, and climate. The wide range of oxidation products and their continuous chemical evolution add complexity to aerosol modelling. To better represent these processes, improved observational constraints and refined chemical mechanisms are needed. An alternative approach is the VBS framework, which, rather than resolving individual chemical pathways, provides a simplified but robust platform for capturing the dynamic partitioning and transformation of organic aerosols.

The VBS framework is a simplified but comprehensive tool for representing organic aerosol compounds. The VBS approach categorizes organic compounds into discrete volatility bins based on their logarithmic C_{sat} values, typically at a reference temperature (Robinson et al., 2007). These bins typically range from highly volatile to extremely low-volatility compounds. By grouping thousands of organic compounds into different volatility bins, the VBS framework helps to reduce the computational complexity while simulating essential processes in a more simplified manner (Shrivastava et al., 2011). As organic compounds undergo oxidation, their volatility decreases

due to the addition of functional groups, causing them to transition into lower C_{sat} bins and promoting their condensation into the particle phase. These transitions are vital for the formation and growth of SOA. Studies such as Jathar et al. (2017), Jiang et al. (2019), and Tsimpidi et al. (2010) have shown that the VBS approach improves the representation of SOA concentrations in the atmosphere and serves as a useful tool to explore the impacts of SOA on air quality and climate.

2.3 Cloud Microphysics

Cloud microphysics encompasses the physical processes that govern the formation, growth, and dissipation of cloud droplets and ice particles. It plays a significant role in cloud lifetime, precipitation processes, and climate interactions. Microphysical properties determine cloud optical properties, radiative effects, and precipitation efficiency, making them a key component in weather and climate modelling (Pruppacher et al., 1998). Thus, understanding cloud microphysics is essential for improving numerical weather prediction and global climate models, as it governs cloud behaviour across both spatial and temporal scales.

Cloud formation occurs when air cools and the water vapour in the air reaches saturation. This saturation causes water vapor to condense onto CCN, activating them to grow into cloud droplets (Houze Jr, 2014). Activation of CCN into cloud droplets is described by Köhler theory, which is based on the balance of surface tension, solute effects, and environmental supersaturation, and thus defines whether aerosol particles can grow into cloud droplets (Pruppacher et al., 1998). The number of activated CCN directly influences CDNC, which plays a key role in defining cloud albedo, microphysical evolution, and precipitation formation (Lohmann & Feichter, 2005). Once activated, cloud droplets grow through condensation of water vapour onto existing droplets, and through collision-coalescence, where larger droplets merge with smaller ones. This process can lead to precipitation formation; however, droplets may also evaporate, particularly in environments with smaller droplet sizes or under certain thermodynamic conditions, which can influence cloud lifetime and its radiative effects (Small et al., 2009).

The role of updraft velocity is also critical in cloud microphysics, as it controls the supersaturation levels in droplet activation (Altaratz et al., 2014). Stronger updrafts increase supersaturation, promoting the activation of more CCN and leading to higher

CDNC (Malavelle et al., 2014). This, in turn, influences cloud optical properties and precipitation processes. In contrast, weaker updrafts produce lower supersaturation levels, limiting CCN activation and resulting in lower CDNC. In **Papers I and III**, we use N_{100} , the sum of aerosol particles larger than 100 nm, as a proxy for modelled CCN concentration (Dusek et al., 2006). However, whether these particles actually activate into cloud droplets depends on the ambient supersaturation: at higher supersaturations, more of the N_{100} particles are likely to activate, while at lower supersaturations, only the larger particles within N_{100} may activate. Since the aerosol activation is primarily dependent on supersaturation, an increase in supersaturation allows smaller aerosol particles to activate, thereby effectively increasing the true CCN concentration (Sihto et al., 2011; Virtanen et al., 2025). Despite this supersaturation dependence, several previous studies have found N_{100} as a reasonable proxy for aerosol activation in low-altitude clouds (Asmi et al., 2012; Portin et al., 2009; Romakkaniemi et al., 2009), including over different marine environments (Sanchez et al., 2023).

Building on this, the relationship between CCN and CDNC becomes increasingly non-linear at high CCN concentrations (Jia & Quaas, 2023; Sihto et al., 2011). At lower CCN concentrations, CDNC initially tends to increase almost linearly with CCN. However, as CCN concentrations continue to rise, competition for available water vapor suppresses supersaturation, which limits further CCN activation (Fanourgakis et al., 2019). Cloud dynamical effects, such as weakened updrafts, can further inhibit droplet formation. Together, these processes result in a complex and difficult-to-ascertain CCN–CDNC relationship, highlighting the challenges in accurately representing aerosol–cloud interactions.

2.4 Susceptibility in Aerosol–Cloud Interactions

An important metric for characterizing aerosol–cloud interactions is the CDNC susceptibility (often referred to as susceptibility). It quantifies how sensitive cloud microphysical properties, particularly the CDNC, are to changes in aerosol concentrations (A), with proxies such as CCN or aerosol optical depth (AOD) commonly used to represent these concentrations. (Gryspeerd et al., 2023; Hasekamp et al., 2019; Quaas et al., 2009). Susceptibility is commonly defined as:

$$S = \frac{d \ln CDNC}{d \ln A}$$

A high susceptibility indicates that even small perturbations in aerosol levels can substantially alter CDNC, which in turn affects cloud albedo, lifetime, and the overall radiative forcing exerted by clouds. Therefore, susceptibility serves as a key parameter in evaluating aerosol indirect effects (Virtanen et al., 2025). However, accurately estimating susceptibility from satellite observations is inherently difficult. Factors such as retrieval uncertainties, cloud heterogeneity, and meteorological confounding factors contribute to this complexity (Arola et al., 2022). Additionally, saturation effects, cloud entrainment, and variability in updraft velocity modulate the strength of aerosol impacts on clouds, making it hard to isolate aerosol-driven changes. In this thesis, susceptibility estimation plays a central role in evaluating aerosol-cloud interaction metrics (see **Paper III**). Addressing its methodological challenges is essential for reducing uncertainties in the climate response to aerosols and for improving satellite-based observational constraints on aerosol indirect effects.

2.5 Modelling Aerosols from Microphysical to Global Scale

Aerosols are subject to many microphysical processes in the atmosphere that place constraints on their size distributions, chemical compositions, and coupling with clouds and radiation. These processes are mathematically represented by a variety of models with different scales, from process-scale models that are focused on fundamental mechanisms operating in the aerosol, to global models that numerically describe aerosol effects in simulations of large scale atmospheric conditions and climate. The following is a brief introduction of the modelling frameworks used to describe aerosol microphysics, from the fundamental governing equations to their applications.

Aerosol microphysics can be described by the general dynamic equation (GDE), which governs the temporal evolution of the aerosol number size distribution $n(v, t)$, where v represents particle volume and t denotes time. GDE provides the theoretical foundation for modelling aerosol physics, which aim to resolve the individual processes governing aerosol lifecycle in detail. The processes include nucleation, condensation, coagulation, and external sources and sinks, which collectively drive changes in the aerosol population:

$$\frac{dn(v, t)}{dt} = \left(\frac{dn(v, t)}{dt} \right)_{\text{nucl}} + \left(\frac{dn(v, t)}{dt} \right)_{\text{cond}} + \left(\frac{dn(v, t)}{dt} \right)_{\text{coag}} + S - R, \quad (4)$$

where $\left(\frac{dn(v,t)}{dt}\right)_{\text{nucl}}$ represents the change in the number of particles due to the formation of new particles through nucleation, $\left(\frac{dn(v,t)}{dt}\right)_{\text{cond}}$ denotes the change in the number of particles of a certain size due to growth by condensation or shrinkage by evaporation, $\left(\frac{dn(v,t)}{dt}\right)_{\text{coag}}$ accounts for the change in particle number due to coagulation. The term S denotes external sources such as primary aerosol emissions, while R represents removal processes including wet and dry deposition (Gelbard & Seinfeld, 1979; Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016).

2.5.1 Process-Scale Modelling

Process-scale aerosol microphysical models, built on the foundation of GDE, explicitly simulate individual microphysical processes governing the evolution of aerosol populations. These models resolve aerosol dynamics, chemistry, or composition at a high level of detail, providing critical insights on the fundamental mechanisms driving different aerosol processes. Examples of such models include the Atmospherically Relevant Chemistry and Aerosol box model (ARCA box) (Clusius et al., 2022), the Lagrangian Model for Analyzing Stationary Observations of NPF events (LMASON model) (Kivekäs et al., 2016), model to Simulate the concentrations of Organic vapours, Sulphuric Acid and Aerosols (SOSAA) (Zhou et al., 2014), and the Aerosol Dynamics, gas- and particle-phase chemistry model for laboratory CHAMber studies (ADCHAM) (Roldin et al., 2014). These models provide a high degree of detail and are extensively used to study fundamental aerosol dynamics in controlled environments, often focusing on specific mechanisms such as nucleation, condensation, and coagulation. They often serve as an essential tool for developing and validating parameterizations that are implemented in global climate models. For example, detailed process-scale simulations of SOA formation help refine the VBS framework, ensuring that SOA representation in global models is physically consistent. One such process-scale model is Model for Coagulation Losses in Nanoparticle Growth (MCOLNAG), which is used in **Paper I** to study the growth of nucleation mode particles and their influence under varying volatility distributions.

Figure 2: Schematic diagrams illustrating a) the grid structure of a typical global aerosol-climate model and b) organic aerosol concentrations simulated by ECHAM-HAMMOZ. It should be noted that the vertical extent of the atmosphere is not to scale in this picture; it has been exaggerated for visualization purposes. Both figures were created using the Paraview visualization software (Kitware, 2025). Figure credits: Tuuli Miinalainen.

2.5.2 Global-Scale Modelling

While process-scale models provide detailed insights into specific aerosol mechanisms, global-scale models extend this understanding to planetary scales, capturing the comprehensive interactions between aerosols, clouds, and climate. These models incorporate more generalized representations of emissions, chemical transformations, microphysical processes, transport, and removal mechanisms. Although the level of detail in global models is typically less than that in process-scale models, they enable the study of aerosol effects on cloud formation, atmospheric chemistry, and climate forcing across larger spatial and temporal scales.

Global models use a grid structure to divide the Earth's atmosphere into three-dimensional grid cells. Each grid cell represents a specific horizontal and vertical domain within which the governing equations of mass, momentum, energy and aerosol processes are solved. Horizontal resolution, typically defined in degrees of latitude and

longitude (eg., $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$), determines the spacing between grid points in the horizontal plane. Vertical resolution, on the other hand, extends through the atmosphere with a number of layers, representing different altitude levels from the surface to the upper atmosphere. Together, these layers and the horizontal grid structure allow for the representation of atmospheric processes across varying heights and latitudes, including atmospheric circulation, boundary layer dynamics, convection, and radiative transfer. While most processes in global models are computed on a grid, the dynamical core of some models, such as the atmospheric general circulation model ECHAM, uses a spectral transform method to solve the equations of atmospheric motion (Roeckner et al., 2004). In this approach, variables are represented in spectral space for computational efficiency and are transformed back to grid space for coupling with physical parameterizations. A schematic representation of horizontal and vertical grid structure in a typical global aerosol-climate model is illustrated in Figure 2. It is worth noting that if the grid resolution is coarser than the scale of certain atmospheric processes, such as cloud microphysics, and small-scale aerosol interactions, these processes cannot be explicitly resolved. Instead, their effects must be approximated through parameterizations, which represent their influence on large-scale dynamics.

A key challenge in global aerosol modelling is accurately representing aerosol microphysics, which governs the size, composition, and growth of aerosol particles. Processes such as nucleation, condensation, and coagulation must be effectively represented to simulate the evolution of aerosol populations. Beyond microphysical and chemical transformations, transport and removal processes further increase the complexity of aerosol modelling. Aerosols are transported across regions, interact with other components of the atmosphere, and are finally removed by dry or wet deposition.

In **Papers I, II, and III**, the global aerosol-climate model ECHAM-HAMMOZ coupled with the aerosol microphysical model Sectional Aerosol module for Large Scale Applications (SALSA) was used to simulate aerosol-cloud interactions. Section 3.1 details more about the model setup used for all the studies along with a brief explanation on how organic aerosols are represented in the model.

2.6 Role of Satellite Observations in Aerosol-Cloud Interaction Studies

Satellite observations play a key role in advancing our understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions. These interactions, which include the influence of aerosols on cloud microphysics, cloud life time, and precipitation processes, require continuous, large-scale observations to study these processes globally, including in remote regions. Satellites offer the ability to monitor aerosols and their interactions with clouds by providing data on key properties such as AOD, particle size, and composition, as well as cloud characteristics such as cloud optical thickness (COT), cloud-top temperature (CTT), and cloud effective radius (CER). Although CDNC is not directly retrieved from the satellite, it can be estimated indirectly, by making use of satellite-retrieved parameters such as COT and CER, combined with assumptions about cloud droplet size distribution, and cloud liquid water content (Arola et al., 2022; Quaas et al., 2006). These estimates depend on several assumptions, such as the adiabaticity of clouds and the homogeneity of cloud physical properties (e.g., cloud geometric thickness) within a satellite pixel, leading to a certain degree of uncertainty in the derived values (Gryspeerdt et al., 2023). Another such variable derived indirectly from satellite data is the liquid water path (LWP), which is defined as the total amount of liquid water present in the atmospheric column. However, a critical limitation with satellite-derived aerosol-cloud interaction studies is the lack of direct measurements of CCN. While the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) provides the variable PSML003_Ocean, representing the column-integrated burden of fine-mode particles over the ocean, it is indirectly derived from satellite-retrieved AOD and has not been thoroughly validated (Rosenfeld et al., 2014). Proxies such as AOD and Aerosol Index are commonly used to infer CCN concentrations and their impact on cloud microphysics (Hasekamp et al., 2019). Aerosol index is calculated as the product of AOD and the Ångström exponent (AE), the latter of which characterizes the spectral dependence of AOD and provides information about particle size distribution.

A significant limitation in analyzing aerosol-cloud interactions over such regions arises from the challenge of mixing different meteorological conditions within a single satellite snapshot. These snapshots often includes multiple meteorological systems, cloud types, and aerosol properties, making it difficult to isolate the sole effects of aerosols on clouds. For instance, the observed changes in cloud microphysics could be a result of aerosol effects, meteorological variability, or both. This ambiguity complicates the attribution

of cloud responses to aerosol perturbations and highlights the need for robust statistical tools to disentangle these effects. Additionally, instrument-related noise and retrieval errors further complicate the extraction of aerosol effects on clouds (Arola et al., 2022; Kokkola et al., 2025).

Another key challenge in satellite-derived aerosol-cloud interaction studies is the difficulty of retrieving aerosol properties under cloudy conditions (Christensen et al., 2017). Passive satellite instruments like MODIS depend on reflected solar radiation to retrieve aerosol properties such as AOD. However, the presence of clouds significantly complicates these retrievals due to their high reflectance, which can obscure or distort the aerosol signal, especially in fully overcast scenes (Remer et al., 2005). As a result, satellite-retrieved aerosol products, such as AOD and CCN values reflect the column-integrated burdens from nearby cloud-free areas surrounding the cloud fields. This means that aerosol properties near the cloud base, where the most critical aerosol-cloud interactions occur, are not directly observable by satellites. Consequently, this limitation adds substantial complexity to studying aerosol-cloud interactions, as the most influential aerosols for cloud formation are often missed in satellite-based observations.

Despite these observational and methodological challenges, accurately quantifying aerosol-cloud interactions from satellite observations remains critical for understanding their influence on cloud properties, atmospheric dynamics, and the Earth's radiative balance. To this end, it is essential to develop robust statistical frameworks and enhance retrieval techniques that can account for confounding factors and make the most of available satellite data, even under complex atmospheric conditions.

3 Methodology

The thesis employs advanced modelling frameworks combined with satellite observations, statistical techniques, and machine learning approaches to investigate aerosol-cloud and aerosol-radiation interaction processes. Global and process-scale models are used to simulate the mechanisms of how the aerosols behave and evolve. Satellite observations provide empirical constraints on aerosol and cloud properties, while machine learning techniques help disentangle aerosol effects on clouds from meteorological influences (such as humidity and wind patterns) and correct for observational biases and measurement uncertainties. These approaches are integrated in this thesis to address the complexities in understanding aerosol-cloud interactions.

The following sections describe the methodological components, starting with modelling approaches, followed by satellite observations, and concluding with advanced statistical and machine learning techniques. **In Papers I, II, and III**, the global aerosol-climate model ECHAM-SALSA was used, while **Paper I** also employed the process-scale growth model MCOLNAG. . In addition, **Paper III** incorporated a cloud parcel model, a radiative transfer model, satellite observations and machine learning techniques.

3.1 Modelling Approaches

3.1.1 Aerosol Microphysics Model

In **Paper I**, we used the Model for Coagulation Losses in Nanoparticle Growth (MCOLNAG) to understand the growth of nucleation mode particles and their survival probability to CCN sizes. This process-scale model explicitly simulates condensation of organic vapours and water onto a monodisperse particle population, while also considering coagulation losses due to interaction with pre-existing aerosols. By focusing solely on aerosol microphysical processes, MCOLNAG allows for a more controlled investigation of how volatility assumptions affect SOA formation and aerosol size distribution. The model tracks the evolution of a monodisperse mode of nucleation-sized particles, where growth is driven by the condensation of organic vapours and water. Condensation is treated using a transition regime mass flux equation that accounts for the

effects of particle motion and vapour molecule volume, which are significant at small particle sizes. (Fuchs & Sutugin, 1970; Lehtinen & Kulmala, 2003). Water uptake is modelled under the assumption of instantaneous equilibrium partitioning between the gas and particle phases, with the particle phase treated as an ideal solution. No explicit particle-phase chemical reactions are considered. A detailed overview of the model and simulation setup is given in **Paper I**.

3.1.2 Cloud Microphysics Model

In **Paper III**, we utilized a cloud parcel model to systematically understand how variations in CCN concentrations and vertical velocity affect CDNC (Kokkola, 2024). This cloud parcel model served as a complementary tool in this satellite-derived aerosol-cloud interactions study to explicitly simulate cloud droplet activation and growth. Since satellite retrievals provide an integrated view of cloud properties over large spatial domains, they are inherently limited in resolving the microphysical processes occurring at the cloud base. We used the model described in Romakkaniemi et al. (2009), which employs a sectional approach to represent aerosol size distribution, with the log-normally spaced particle size bins evolving dynamically during condensation and evaporation. The model was initialized using aerosol size distributions and meteorological conditions derived from observational constraints over the Northern Pacific Ocean as provided by Park et al. (2020) to ensure consistency with the satellite datasets analysed in **paper III**.

To systematically investigate the impact of aerosol concentrations and updraft velocity on CDNC, we performed sensitivity simulations by modifying the total number concentrations in the Aitken and accumulation modes. By increasing and decreasing the aerosol concentrations from the baseline values reported by Park et al. (2020), we examined how different aerosol loading conditions affect cloud droplet formation. We also varied vertical velocity between 0.1 ms^{-1} and 0.6 ms^{-1} to simulate different dynamic regimes. The cloud parcel model simulations were run until the air parcel reached an altitude, approximately 250 m above the prescribed cloud base height of 1000 m. In our analysis, particles with diameters greater than 100 nm were classified as CCN, while those exceeding $2 \mu\text{m}$ were considered cloud droplets.

3.1.3 Radiative Transfer Model

Radiative transfer modelling (RTM) is a fundamental component in atmospheric sciences, particularly in understanding the interactions between radiation and atmospheric constituents such as gases, aerosols, and cloud particles. RTM offers a robust framework for modelling the propagation of electromagnetic radiation through the atmosphere (Deutschmann et al., 2011).

In **Paper III**, we estimated satellite-derived cloud base updraft velocity using libRadtran version 2.0.5 (Library for Radiative Transfer) (Emde et al., 2016), following the parameterization by Zheng et al. (2016). The simulations of solar and terrestrial radiative fluxes performed with libRadtran enabled the calculation of cloud top radiative cooling (CTRC) based on satellite-retrieved cloud properties. Zheng et al. (2016) formulated a relationship between CTRC and cloud base updraft velocity, which was quantified as described in Section 3.2.2.

The radiative transfer equation in libRadtran was solved using DISORT (Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer Solver), which assumes a 1-D plane-parallel atmosphere (Chandrasekhar, 2013; Stamnes et al., 1988). The DISORT method accounts for multiple scattering, absorption, and emission from the atmosphere with high accuracy and is, therefore, well suited for studying aerosol-cloud-radiation interactions. Atmospheric absorption was represented using k-correlated absorption cross-sections, parameterized following Kato et al. (1999) for solar radiation and Fu and Liou (1992) for thermal infrared radiation. Aerosol optical properties were incorporated using the Shettle (1990) maritime aerosol parameterization, which is particularly suitable for our study over the Pacific Ocean. More details on the model setup can be found in **Paper III**.

3.1.4 Global Aerosol-Climate Model: ECHAM-HAMMOZ

In **Papers I, II and III**, we employed the global aerosol climate model ECHAM-HAMMOZ (ECHAM6.3-HAM2.3) (Schultz et al., 2018) to simulate various physical and chemical processes of aerosols and their climatic impacts. ECHAM-HAMMOZ is a comprehensive global model that integrates advanced physical and chemical treatments of aerosols with meteorological and radiative processes. The ECHAM general circulation model is coupled with the HAM aerosol module (Tegen et al., 2019) and the

SALSA microphysics scheme (Kokkola et al., 2018) to assess the dynamics of aerosols, their influence on cloud formation, and their impact on the Earth’s energy balance.

ECHAM is the global atmospheric general circulation model that solves the equations of motion and continuity within the atmosphere (Stevens et al., 2013). ECHAM utilises a spectral representation for horizontal resolution, integrating vertical levels with a hybrid-sigma pressure coordinate system. This approach facilitates an accurate representation of atmospheric processes from the surface to the upper atmosphere (Roeckner et al., 2004). **In Papers I, II, and III**, all simulations utilized the T63 spectral truncation for horizontal resolution, which corresponds to a grid spacing of approximately $1.9^\circ \times 1.9^\circ$, along with 47 hybrid sigma-pressure levels for vertical resolution.

The HAM (Hamburg Aerosol Module) coupled with ECHAM offers a detailed representation of aerosol processes, including emissions, transport, chemical transformations, and removal (Tegen et al., 2019). HAM simulates key aerosol species, including sulfate, BC, OC, sea salt, and dust, while capturing their size distribution, mixing state, and interactions with clouds and radiation. HAM employs two approaches for modelling aerosol microphysics: the modal scheme (M7) and the sectional scheme (SALSA), each presenting distinct trade-offs regarding computational efficiency and physical accuracy.

The M7 scheme employs a modal approach incorporating seven log-normal modes to characterise nucleation, Aitken, accumulation, and coarse-mode particles (Stier et al., 2005; Vignati et al., 2004). The M7 scheme is computationally efficient for large-scale climate simulations; however, it has certain limitations due to its fixed log-normal modes. The uniform properties assumed within each mode may oversimplify key processes such as condensation, coagulation, and hygroscopic growth, potentially resulting in inaccuracies in the representation of aerosol size distributions (Baklanov et al., 2014). For example, the modal approach may struggle to accurately represent the variability in the size distribution, especially the mean sizes of individual modes (Korhola et al., 2014).

To address these limitations, SALSA adopts a sectional approach, representing aerosols in discrete size bins rather than predefined modes (Kokkola et al., 2008). This allows each bin to evolve independently through processes such as nucleation, condensation, and deposition, resulting in a better representation of aerosol microphysics. However, the sectional approach is computationally much heavier compared to modal schemes, making it more demanding for large-scale climate simulations.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of aerosol size and composition distribution in SALSA. The chemical compounds are sulfate (SU), black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), mineral dust (DU) and sea salt (SS).

The aerosol size distribution in SALSA is divided into 10 size classes, ranging from 3 nm to 10 μm . These bins are further categorized into two subranges to effectively capture aerosol growth dynamics. The first subrange, spanning 3 nm to 50 nm, comprises three bins that include the smallest particles responsible for nucleation and early growth. The second subrange covers particles ranging from 50 nm to 10 μm , which includes larger particles that are crucial for CCN activation and cloud formation. Aerosols within this subrange are categorised into two classes based on their external mixing: one where insoluble compounds are emitted to and the other one where soluble compounds are emitted to. Figure 3 presents a schematic representation of aerosol size and composition distribution in SALSA. Cloud droplet activation in SALSA is solved using the parameterization described by Abdul-Razzak and Ghan (2002). SALSA, with its robust representation of aerosol processes, serves as an effective platform for investigating aerosol-cloud-climate interactions across various spatial scales (e.g., (Andersson et al., 2015; Bergman et al., 2011; Holopainen et al., 2022; Kühn et al., 2020; Miinalainen et al., 2021; Tonttila et al., 2017)). The coupling of SALSA into the global climate model ECHAM-HAMMOZ provides a robust framework for analyzing aerosol impacts on atmospheric and climatic systems. This capability is particularly crucial for our research, and thus we made use of the strengths of SALSA for simulating aerosol-cloud

interactions in **Papers I, II, and III**.

3.1.4.1 Volatility Basis Set (VBS) in SALSA

In SALSA, organic mass is emitted both as primary organic matter (POM) and in the form of VOCs such as monoterpenes and isoprene. Monoterpenes include α -pinene, β -pinene, *t*- β -ocimene, sabinene, limonene, myrcene, and 3-carene. Anthropogenic VOCs considered include toluene, xylene, and benzene. Once emitted, these VOCs undergo gas-phase oxidation, transforming into low-volatility compounds that can condense onto pre-existing particles. The oxidation products are driven by the reaction of VOCs with major atmospheric oxidants. During the daytime, OH, and O₃ act as the primary oxidants, while at night, NO₃ dominate. In **Papers I, II, and III**, the concentrations of these oxidants in SALSA coupled with HAM are defined using the MACC reanalysis data, which covers an 8-year long reanalysis of atmospheric composition data (Inness et al., 2013). ECHAM-HAMMOZ also offers the possibility to prescribe the concentrations of these oxidants using 3D climatological means derived by a chemistry model.

By default, SALSA employs a simplified three-bin VBS framework to represent the VOC oxidation products (Mielonen et al., 2018; Stadtler et al., 2018). This three-bin setup, with C_{sat} values of 0, 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, provides a computationally efficient way to capture the volatility distribution of organic vapours. However, its coarse resolution limits its ability to accurately represent organic vapours that span a broad range of volatilities. This limitation becomes particularly important when studying monoterpene derived SOA, as monoterpenes are a significant class of biogenic SOA precursors, especially in boreal regions (Kayes & Mallik, 2020; Rinne et al., 2009). These biogenic VOCs are emitted in large quantities by vegetation and undergo oxidation in the atmosphere, forming a diverse spectrum of oxidation products with volatilities ranging from ELVOCs, to SVOCs (Jokinen et al., 2015). Monoterpenes also play a key role in global aerosol formation and their subsequent climate impacts (Zhang et al., 2018).

The reliability of the VBS framework in facilitating the simulation of SOA formation is highly dependent on the the accuracy of volatility distribution representing organic compounds (Shrivastava et al., 2011). Uncertainties in this distribution can lead to significant biases in SOA mass predictions, CCN activity, and their climatic effects. However, the sensitivity of global-model simulated SOA mass, CCN, and radiative effects to volatility distribution of organics remains inadequately studied. To address

this, we implemented a comprehensive nine-bin VBS setup in SALSA for monoterpene oxidation products, as described in **Paper I**. This setup provides a detailed representation of gas-particle partitioning, improving the model’s capability to explore the potential impacts of varying volatility distributions on aerosol properties and their subsequent climatic effects. The volatility distribution of VBS bins in this nine-bin setup span $C_{sat} = 10^{-4}$ to $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, formulated based on the experimental data from Tröstl et al. (2016) and Hunter et al. (2017). The lower-volatility bins (ELVOCs and LVOCs) were derived from Tröstl et al. (2016), while the semi-volatile and higher-volatility compounds were adapted from Hunter et al. (2017). The stoichiometric coefficients, denoted as α , represent the fraction of reacted VOC mass that forms oxidation products within specific volatility classes. The C_{sat} values and the corresponding stoichiometric coefficients for the nine-bin VBS setup are given in Table 1.

To systematically evaluate the sensitivity of SOA formation to uncertainties in the above described volatility distribution, we conducted a series of simulations where we perturbed the assumed volatility distribution of monoterpene oxidation products. Specifically, in **Paper I**, we performed a sensitivity analysis where we increased and decreased C_{sat} values by a factor of 10 to examine how these changes influence SOA mass burden, CCN concentrations, and radiative effects. This approach enabled us to quantify how uncertainties in precursor volatility affect the growth and survival of particles reaching CCN sizes and their impact on aerosol-cloud interactions.

Despite its advantages, the nine-bin VBS setup is computationally expensive, particularly for global model simulations. Many global models, including CESM2 (Tilmes et al., 2019), GEOS-CHEM (Fritz et al., 2022), GFDL AM (Zheng et al., 2023), and the default version of ECHAM-SALSA (Mielonen et al., 2018) employ VBS configurations with fewer bins. To assess the trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency, we also formulated a three-bin VBS setup, aggregating bins from the nine-bin setup. The stoichiometric coefficients for the three-bin setup were derived by summing the coefficients of the merged bins, as shown in Table 1. This facilitates the direct comparison between three-bin and nine-bin setups on the sensitivity of VBS bin resolution to SOA formation and climate effects.

Table 1: Overview of Saturation Concentrations and Stoichiometric Coefficients used for 9-Bin and 3-Bin VBS setups

Nine-Bin VBS		Three-Bin VBS		
C_{sat} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	α	C_{sat} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	α	Bin
0	0.0038			
10^{-4}	0.0029	4.8×10^{-4}	0.0126	Bin 1
10^{-3}	0.0059			
10^{-2}	0.0146			
10^{-1}	0.016	5.48×10^{-1}	0.0639	Bin 2
10^0	0.0333			
10^1	0.1028			
10^2	0.1456	5.32×10^2	0.497	Bin 3
10^3	0.2491			

3.1.4.2 SOA routine in SALSA

SALSA includes a comprehensive framework for simulating the formation and evolution of SOA, which significantly influence the aerosol population. The size resolved sectional approach in SALSA facilitates detailed modelling of gas-particle partitioning of the oxidized organic compounds based on their volatility. SALSA estimates the partitioning of VOC oxidation products between the gas and particle phases using the Analytical Predictor of Condensation (APC) by numerically solving the condensation equation:

$$\frac{dC_{\text{org},i}}{dt} = k_{m,i} (C_{\text{org},i,\text{surf}} - C_{\text{org},i,\text{gas}}), \quad (5)$$

where $C_{\text{org},i}$ represents the gas-phase concentration of the organic compound for the size section i , while $k_{m,i}$ is the mass transfer coefficient. $C_{\text{org},i,\text{surf}}$ denotes the equilibrium concentration of the condensing organic compound at the particle surface, and $C_{\text{org},i,\text{gas}}$ is the gas-phase concentration of the organic compound. This approach allows for the estimation of non-equilibrium partitioning of each organic compound between the gas phase and aerosol size classes, thereby enabling detailed modelling of SOA formation.

With a too long time step for this numerically stiff problem, there is oscillatory behaviour where condensation and evaporation alternate in consecutive time steps. To avoid this, the equations are solved using five sub-time steps within one model time step. The sub-time step length increases logarithmically. The surface equilibrium concentration $C_{\text{org},i,\text{surf}}$ is calculated using:

$$C_{\text{org},i,\text{surf}} = S'_i x_{\text{org},i} C_{\text{org},\text{sat}}, \quad (6)$$

where S'_i represents the Kelvin effect, $x_{\text{org},i}$ is the mole fraction of the organic compound in the condensed phase, and $C_{\text{org},\text{sat}}$ is the saturation concentration of the organic compound. The concentrations are expressed in mole concentrations (mol m^{-3}), derived from mass-based values, and assuming ideal behaviour in the condensed phase (Kokkola et al., 2014).

This method offers an efficient approach to simulating condensation processes while maintaining numerical stability. By combining these equations, the APC method captures the complex interactions governing gas-particle partitioning and the growth of SOA across different aerosol size classes.

3.2 Satellite Observations in aerosol-cloud interactions

In **Paper III**, we analyzed observed aerosol-cloud interactions using Level-2 (L2) satellite retrievals from the MODIS onboard the Aqua and Terra satellites. The MOD06.L2 and MYD06.L2 cloud products from Collection 6.1 (Platnick et al., 2015) provided key cloud properties, such as COT, CER, CTT, and cloud top height (CTH). MODIS aerosol products, MOD04.L2 and MYD04.L2 offered AOD and AE (Levy et al., 2013). AOD acts as a proxy for the total aerosol burden within the atmospheric column, while AE provides information regarding aerosol size distribution. Higher AE values imply a predominance of fine-mode particles, whereas reduced values suggest a large presence of coarse-mode aerosols, such as dust or sea salt. To obtain the satellite-derived CCN concentration, we utilized MODIS CCN data (PSML003_Ocean), which provides the column-integrated burden of fine-mode particles over the ocean (Gassó & Hegg, 2003; Levy et al., 2013). This dataset was favoured over AOD or aerosol index due to its more direct representation of CCN concentrations. Since aerosol index, defined as the product of AOD and AE, accounts for the spectral dependence of AOD, it was also

utilized in **Paper III** as a supplementary metric to enhance the robustness of our analysis (Hasekamp et al., 2019). In order to minimise pixel-level variability and improve data robustness, all cloud and aerosol data were aggregated to a spatial resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$, following recommendations from Grosvenor et al. (2018). This aggregation reduces small-scale variability and enhances the statistical robustness of aerosol-cloud interaction analyses.

3.2.1 Retrieval of CDNC and LWP from MODIS Data

Since MODIS does not directly retrieve CDNC and LWP, these properties were derived using empirical relationships based on COT and CER, as proposed by Quaas et al. (2006):

$$\text{CDNC} = \alpha \tau_c^{0.5} r_e^{-2.5} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{LWP} = \frac{5}{9} \rho_w r_e \tau_c \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha = 1.37 \times 10^{-5} m^{-0.5}$ is a constant, ρ_w is the density of liquid water (assumed to be 1000 kg m^{-3}), τ_c is the COT, and r_e is the CER. In our calculations, we followed the adiabatic cloud assumptions outlined in Quaas et al. (2006), where cloud liquid water content is assumed to be a constant fraction of its adiabatic value, CDNC remains uniform throughout the cloud column, and CER is proportional to the volume mean radius. To ensure the reliability of the datasets, we applied filtering procedures consistent with those recommended by Gryspeerd et al. (2019). Specifically, we focused only on single-layer liquid clouds with a top warmer than 268 K at a 1 km resolution. We also excluded pixels with COT values less than 4 or CER less than $4 \mu\text{m}$. These thresholds were chosen to avoid the increased uncertainty associated with retrievals at lower COT and CER values, thereby enhancing the accuracy and robustness of our CDNC and LWP calculations. By adhering to standardized filtering protocols, we aimed to minimize biases and uncertainties in our dataset (Arola et al., 2022), enabling more accurate assessments of aerosol-cloud interactions and their impacts on cloud properties.

3.2.2 Estimation of Updraft Velocity

The cloud base updraft velocity (W_b) plays a crucial role in understanding aerosol-cloud interactions through its influence on CCN activation and hence CDNC. However, direct measurements of W_b from remote-sensing based observations are not widely available, necessitating indirect estimation methods. **Paper III** employs a radiative approach to estimate W_b , using CTRC as a proxy based on the strong correlation between W_b and CTRC established by Zheng et al. (2016). The parametrization used to calculate W_b from CTRC is as follows:

$$W_b = 0.44 \times \text{CTRC} + 22.30 \pm 13, \quad (9)$$

where W_b and CTRC have units of cm/s and W/m², respectively. We simulated the radiative properties of the atmosphere and cloud layers for all cloudy pixels from satellite data to estimate W_b using libRadtran. Each cloudy pixel was analyzed separately using local characteristics such as time, longitude and latitude, surface albedo, cloud cover and the vertical profile of cloud liquid water content. A detailed description of the libRadtran model is given in Section 3.1.3.

The input data used for the RTM in simulating CTRC consisted of a combination of MODIS cloud products and ERA-5 reanalysis data. Key cloud properties retrieved from MODIS include CTT, CTH, COT, and CER. The ERA-5 reanalysis data further contributed necessary information such as surface albedo, surface pressure, humidity, and temperature (Hersbach et al., 2020). Assuming adiabatic clouds, the cloud geometric thickness (CGT) was calculated using LWP following Brenguier et al. (2000). The cloud base height was estimated as the difference between CTH and CGT. The vertical profile of cloud liquid water content was computed for each modal layer following Wood et al. (2009).

3.3 Regression Methods

Understanding the relationship between CCN and CDNC is an important aspect for better assessing aerosol-cloud interactions. Since both CCN and CDNC are subject to some degree of measurement uncertainties, selecting an appropriate regression method

is particularly essential. In **Paper III**, we use OLS in its two-dimensional form (Dismuke & Lindrooth, 2006) and BLS (York et al., 2004) regression techniques to analyze their logarithmic relationship. OLS estimates the linear relationship between CCN and CDNC by minimizing the sum of squared residuals:

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2. \quad (10)$$

where y_i (log-transformed CDNC) is modeled as a function of x_i (log-transformed CCN):

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \epsilon_i. \quad (11)$$

Here, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 is the slope, and ϵ_i is the error term (Dismuke & Lindrooth, 2006). While OLS is widely used, it assumes no error in the independent variable, which can bias susceptibility estimates in aerosol-cloud studies (Mikkonen et al., 2019; Pitkänen et al., 2016). BLS addresses the limitations of OLS by accounting for uncertainties in both CCN and CDNC:

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{(y_i - \beta_0 - \beta_1 x_i)^2}{\sigma_y^2} + \frac{(x_i - \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 y_i)^2}{\sigma_x^2} \right), \quad (12)$$

where σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 represent measurement uncertainties in CCN and CDNC, respectively (York et al., 2004). By comparing OLS and BLS, we evaluate their impact on estimating aerosol-cloud susceptibility, highlighting how regression choice influences the interpretation of aerosol effects on cloud microphysics.

3.4 Machine Learning Techniques

Machine learning methods are increasingly gaining attention in atmospheric sciences, particularly for analyzing highly complex processes like aerosol-cloud interaction (Gao et al., 2024; Kalbande et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2022; Miinalainen et al., 2023; Redemann & Gao, 2024). In **Paper III**, we primarily utilized two key machine learning

methods: Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001) for feature selection and Elastic Net Regression (ENR) for estimating the CCN-CDNC slope.

The RF, an ensemble learning method that constructs multiple decision trees and combines their predictions, was applied to evaluate the influence of key variables on the variability of CDNC (Chen et al., 2022; Miinalainen et al., 2023; Nair & Yu, 2020). The RF approach is particularly advantageous for high-dimensional data analysis and determining the relative importance of input features. The RF model was implemented using the scikit-learn Python library (Pedregosa et al., 2011), incorporating hyperparameter optimization through grid search and cross-validation. The feature importance ranking derived from RF analysis allowed us to identify the atmospheric and meteorological variables that most significantly influenced CDNC. The analysis, conducted independently for satellite observations and climate model datasets, revealed that CCN burden, LWP, and W_b were the primary predictors in both datasets. The RF-derived feature rankings were also compared with SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) (Lundberg & Lee, 2017) and permutation feature importance (Altmann et al., 2010), which corroborated that the identified key features were consistent with those concluded by RF feature importance.

Following feature selection, we evaluated multiple machine learning models to predict CDNC and to estimate the CCN-CDNC relationship. The models included ENR (Friedman et al., 2010), RF (Breiman, 2001), XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016), Support Vector Regression (SVR) (Drucker et al., 1999), Gradient Boosting (Friedman, 2001), LightGBM (Ke et al., 2017), and a Neural Network using a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) (Pinkus, 1999). Out of all these methods, ENR outperformed the other models, yielding the highest coefficient of determination (R^2) value and the lowest mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) for both satellite and climate model datasets. ENR differs from common regression techniques as it incorporates both L1 (Lasso) and L2 (Ridge) regularization approaches to address multicollinearity and over-fitting. The combination enables the ENR to take into account the linear and nonlinear dependencies without compromising interpretability (Friedman et al., 2010; Zou & Hastie, 2005).

The ENR model minimizes the following loss function:

$$\text{minimize} \left(\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \alpha \rho \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| + \frac{\alpha(1-\rho)}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \right), \quad (13)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i are the observed and predicted CDNC values, respectively, N represents the number of observations, β_j are the regression coefficients corresponding to predictor variable j , and α and ρ control the strength of regularization. To further optimize ENR performance, we conducted a grid search over a range of hyperparameters and selected values that minimized the root mean square error (RMSE) while ensuring interpretability. The optimal hyperparameters were found to be $\alpha = 0.1$ for satellite data and $\alpha = 0.01$ for climate model data, with $\rho = 0.1$ for both datasets.

4 Key Results and discussion

This section presents the key findings of this work, focusing on the impact of aerosols on cloud microphysics and climate. First, we present the effect of uncertainties in volatility distributions of organic vapours on SOA mass, CCN concentrations and radiative forcing, along with comparing different resolutions of the VBS bins in a global aerosol-climate model. Next, we present the radiative forcing associated with alternative wood use scenarios over Finland, evaluating how different biomass utilization strategies influence aerosol emissions and their subsequent climate effects. Finally, we address the challenges in traditional regression methods for estimating the susceptibility of aerosol perturbations to cloud droplet formation, particularly the CCN-CDNC relationship. We introduce an alternative machine-learning based approach that improves the accuracy and robustness of slope estimation, overcoming limitations associated with conventional regression techniques.

4.1 Sensitivity of SOA Formation and Radiative Effects to the Volatilities of Semi-Volatile Organics

In **Paper I**, we studied the complex interactions between SOA formation and their volatility distribution using both process-level and global-scale models. To first investigate the influence of volatility distribution on SOA formation and CCN concentration at the process level, we used the MCOLNAG particle growth model, simulating SOA formation under different volatility assumptions. We found that, in a monodisperse aerosol framework, shifting the volatilities of monoterpene oxidation products by an order of magnitude had a strong influence on the growth of nucleation-mode particles and their survival to CCN-relevant sizes. When the volatilities were shifted to lower values, organic vapours became more prone to condensation, increasing particle growth rates and reducing the time available for coagulation losses. As a result, a larger fraction of nucleation-mode particles survived to 100 nm. Conversely, shifting the volatilities to higher values resulted in slower particle growth, leading to a significant reduction in the survival fraction of particles reaching 100 nm. This highlights that uncertainties in volatility directly affect simulated particle survival probabilities, which in turn impacts CCN concentrations. The impact of volatility was further examined under different total organic vapour concentrations, revealing a dependence of SOA sensitivity on pre-

Figure 4: Simulated SOA burden of (a) VBS \times 1 and the relative difference between (b) VBS \times 10 and (c) VBS \times 0.1 with respect to VBS \times 1 over the boreal region. Figure adapted from **Paper I**.

cursor availability. At lower vapour concentrations, the fraction of nucleation-mode particles reaching CCN sizes was generally lower, making the system more sensitive to volatility shifts. At higher vapour concentrations, a greater fraction of nucleation-mode particles survived, and hence their sensitivity to volatility changes was reduced. These findings suggest that, at the process level, SOA formation and CCN activation strongly depend on the assumed volatility distribution.

Scaling up the investigation, we used the global aerosol–climate model ECHAM-SALSA to assess the impact of volatility shifts on SOA burden and CCN concentrations. This analysis was conducted not only on a global scale, but also in a framework where aerosol number and composition are size-dependent, and all atmospheric processes influence

Figure 5: Fraction of particle phase mass concentration close to the ground level in each of the VBS bins with shifted volatilities over the boreal region. The x-axis values show the C_{sat} of that bin in the VBS \times 1 simulation. Figure adapted from **Paper I**.

the aerosol population. The global model analysis in **Paper I** focused specifically on the boreal region during the summer months, a period when monoterpene emissions are high (Vanhatalo et al., 2020). Figure 4 shows the simulated SOA burden for the baseline volatility assumption (VBS \times 1), as well as the relative differences in SOA burden when the volatilities were shifted by an order of magnitude (VBS \times 10 and VBS \times 0.1). We found that a tenfold decrease in volatility (VBS \times 0.1) increased SOA burden by 13%, while a tenfold increase (VBS \times 10) led to a 9% reduction. We also analyzed the response of CCN concentrations to volatility shifts by examining N_{100} , the number concentration of particles exceeding a diameter of 100 nm. While the effect of volatility on SOA burden was substantial, the response of CCN concentrations was more moderate. The relative differences in N_{100} ranged from -2% to -7% for VBS \times 10 and +1% to +5% for VBS \times 0.1 compared to the VBS \times 1 simulation.

The modelled shifts in SOA burden and particle number concentration could be attributed to the gas–particle partitioning of organic compounds (Figure 5). Specifically, lower-volatility bins ($C_{sat} \leq 10^{-1} \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), tend to partition almost all of their mass to particle phase regardless of the volatility shift, making SOA formation relatively insensitive to uncertainties in these bins. These bins play a significant role in the growth of the smallest particles to CCN sizes. However, bins with higher C_{sat} values ($100\text{--}10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) which have more influence on particle masses in larger particles already hav-

ing reached CCN sizes, exhibited notable shifts in partitioning behaviour, contributing significantly to changes in SOA burden. Hence, while the overall mass changes with volatility shifts, the CCN concentration and CDNC may remain relatively unchanged.

Given the computational expense of high-resolution volatility representations, many models adopt simplified three-bin VBS schemes instead of more detailed VBS setups with more bins. To evaluate the impact of this simplification, we compared the simulations using the nine-bin VBS setup with those using a three-bin VBS setup. In the three-bin VBS setup, we combined adjacent bins from the nine-bin VBS setup to form three bins. Each bin in the three-bin VBS setup is represented as Bin 1, Bin 2 and Bin 3 by order of increasing volatility. Our simulations in ECHAM-SALSA with the nine-bin VBS setup resulted in an 18 % higher SOA mass concentration compared to the three-bin setup, especially at ground level. The discrepancy primarily arises from the way volatilities are lumped together in the three-bin setup, which affects the partitioning behaviour of semi-volatile organics. Interestingly, the difference in N_{100} between the two setups was in the opposite direction compared to SOA mass. Specifically, the three-bin VBS setup resulted in 70 % higher N_{100} at 500 hPa, although near the surface, differences were only around 5 %.

We also performed a series of simulations using the three-bin VBS setup to understand the sensitivity of SOA mass and CCN concentrations to uncertainties in the volatilities of individual VBS bins. We shifted the volatility of one VBS bin at a time by 1-order of magnitude while keeping the volatilities of all other bins unchanged. Shifting Bin 1, the lowest-volatility bin and Bin 2 in the three-bin VBS setup had negligible effects on both SOA mass and N_{100} . This is because, as discussed earlier, low-volatility compounds ($C_{\text{sat}} \leq 10^{-1} \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) almost entirely partition to the particle phase, making their condensation largely insensitive to small changes in volatility assumptions. However, Bin 3, which represents the most volatile organic fraction, exhibited a notable response to volatility changes. Increasing the volatility of Bin 3 by a factor of 10 led to a 5 % decrease in SOA mass and a 2 % reduction in N_{100} , while decreasing its volatility caused a 20 % increase in SOA mass and a 9 % increase in N_{100} . This suggests that uncertainties in the volatility of semi-volatile compounds play a dominant role in determining aerosol growth and CCN activation. These findings emphasize the critical role of carefully selecting the volatility parameters in VBS models, particularly when using a coarser three-bin setup.

Finally, we examined how these variations translated into changes in radiative effects

Figure 6: Summer mean (a) Top of the atmosphere IRF_{ARI} and (b) ERF when the volatility of individual volatility bins are shifted with respect to the original volatility employing three-bin VBS setup calculated over the boreal forest region. Error bars show $1-\sigma$ standard deviation of the data across all the grid cells. Figure adapted from **Paper I**.

due to volatility shifts, primarily through aerosol–radiation and aerosol–cloud interactions. We estimated IRF_{ARI} and ERF for different volatility scenarios over the boreal region using nudged climate model simulations. While we use the term radiative forcing in **Paper I**, it is important to clarify that, in the strictest sense, we are referring to the changes in radiative effects that arise specifically from variations in volatility. For the nine-bin VBS setup, increasing SOA volatility ($VBS \times 10$) led to a $+0.16 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ increase in IRF_{ARI} , while decreasing volatility ($VBS \times 0.1$) resulted in a -0.20 W m^{-2} decrease in IRF_{ARI} . The corresponding ERF values were $+0.35 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and -0.40 W m^{-2} , respectively, demonstrating that the distribution of SOA volatility can lead to significant differences in radiative effects. The comparison between the nine-bin and three-bin VBS setups also revealed a $+0.25 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ IRF_{ARI} and -1.25 W m^{-2} ERF for the three-bin setup relative to the nine-bin setup.

To further investigate the role of individual volatility bins in shaping radiative effects, we conducted a sensitivity analysis within the three-bin VBS setup, changing the volatility of each bin separately (Figure 6). The results show that shifting the volatility of bin 1 has negligible effects on radiative forcing, aligning with its limited

contribution to SOA burden and CCN concentrations. However, shifting the volatilities of Bin 2 leads to minor effects on both IRF_{ARI} and ERF. The most pronounced effects arise from changes to bin 3, which represents the highest-volatility compounds. A decrease in the volatility of bin 3 leads to an IRF_{ARI} of $-0.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and an ERF of $+0.8 \pm 2.24 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, whereas an increase in its volatility leads to an IRF_{ARI} of $+0.05 \pm 0.04 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and an ERF of $+0.45 \pm 2.3 \text{ W m}^{-2}$.

4.2 Radiative Forcing from Aerosol Emissions Under Alternate Wood Use Scenarios

In **Paper II**, we investigated the impact of alternate forest biomass use on aerosol emissions and radiative forcing over Finland. This study included four alternate wood use scenarios, each involving an increase in harvest of 10 million m^3 compared to the baseline. The additional harvest is allocated to saw logs, pulp wood, or energy biomass, which is then combusted either in small-scale appliances or in medium-to-large scale boilers.

The baseline scenario reflected the recent annual roundwood harvest of 70 million m^3 , with allocations as follows: 28 million m^3 for saw logs, 31.5 million m^3 for pulp wood, and 10.5 million m^3 for energy biomass (LUKE, 2024). Saw logs are primarily used for sawn wood and plywood, while, pulp wood is used for pulp-based products. The residual biomass from saw log and pulp production is allocated as energy biomass and is combusted in large-scale boilers for energy production. In the alternative scenarios, the harvest level was increased to 80 million m^3 , the maximum sustainable level in Finland (Natural Resources Institute Finland, 2024). The additional 10 million m^3 was allocated to saw logs (80SW), pulp wood (80PW), or energy biomass for combustion in either small-scale appliances (80EB SSB) or large-scale boilers (80EB LSB). In the 80SW scenario, increased saw log harvest replaced steel and concrete production, reducing emissions typically associated with these materials. In the 80PW scenario, half of the additional pulp wood was used to produce viscose-based textiles, replacing polyester, and the other half was used for cardboard, replacing High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) plastic, both contributing to emission reductions. In the 80EB scenarios, increased energy biomass was assumed to replace fossil fuels such as natural gas, peat, oil, and coal by 25%, leading to reduced emissions from energy production.

Overall, the increased biomass harvest, when reallocated to more sustainable uses such as replacing fossil fuels and plastics, resulted in a net reduction in emissions, despite the overall increase in biomass production. The scenarios and their effects on emissions are summarized in Table 1 of **Paper II**.

Table 2: Changes in BC, OC, and SO₂ emissions in industrial and energy sectors due to alternative scenarios compared to the baseline scenario.

Scenario	BC _{industry} t year ⁻¹	BC _{energy} t year ⁻¹	OC _{industry} t year ⁻¹	OC _{energy} t year ⁻¹	SO ₂ _{industry} t year ⁻¹	SO ₂ _{energy} t year ⁻¹
Baseline						
80SW	0.6		0.5		63.3	
80PW	-118.1		-94.5		-4487.2	
80EB SSB 2020–2030		2395.0		1916.0		-2683.5
80EB LSB 2020–2030		-10.3		-8.2		-1789.7

The emission impacts of these different biomass allocation scenarios are shown in Table 2. In the 80SW scenario, annual BC and OC emissions increased slightly (+0.6 t and +0.5 t, respectively), whereas SO₂ emissions rose significantly (+63.3 t) compared to the baseline scenario. In contrast, the 80PW scenario exhibited a substantial decrease in emissions, with BC, OC, and SO₂ reducing by -118.1 t, -94.5 t, and -4487.2 t, respectively. The 80EB SSB scenario showed an increase in BC and OC emissions but a reduction in SO₂ emissions. Meanwhile, the 80EB LSB scenario led to lower emissions for all three components compared to the baseline scenario. These emission trends are critical in determining the subsequent impact of aerosols on atmospheric composition and radiative forcing.

The resulting changes in emissions translated to distinct impacts on IRF_{ARI} and ERF. The 80EB SSB and 80PW scenarios resulted in slightly positive IRF_{ARI} values (+0.007 W m⁻² and +0.0014 W m⁻², respectively), though the uncertainty associated with these estimates tend to be relatively high. In contrast, the 80EB LSB and 80SW scenarios exhibited slightly negative IRF_{ARI} values (-0.0130 W m⁻² and -0.0061 W m⁻², respectively).

The spatial distribution of IRF_{ARI} varied across Finland, reflecting differences in regional emission patterns as shown in Figure 7. In the 80EB SSB scenario, increased BC and OC emissions resulted in marginal warming effect across most of Finland, as

Figure 7: Effect of alternate wood use scenarios on IRF_{ARI} of anthropogenic forest-based aerosols in Finland. Figure adapted from **Paper II**.

BC absorption slightly outweighed the cooling effect of OC and SO_2 reduction. The 80EB LSB scenario exhibited a widespread cooling effect, largely driven by reductions in BC and OC emissions and sustained sulfate formation. Similarly, the 80SW scenario showed minor cooling over Finland, except in the southernmost regions, due to a slight increase in BC, OC, and SO_2 emissions. Despite reductions in BC and OC emissions, the 80PW scenario led to a warming effect over central Finland due to a substantial decline in SO_2 emissions, which limited the formation of sulfate aerosols.

The ERF estimates revealed stronger climate effects than IRF_{ARI} . The 80PW scenario resulted in a positive ERF ($+0.1338 \text{ W m}^{-2}$), primarily due to the substantial reduction in SO_2 emissions, which led to fewer sulfate aerosols and a weakened cloud albedo effect. In contrast, the 80EB SSB, 80EB LSB, and 80SW scenarios exhibited negative ERF values (-0.9725 W m^{-2} , -0.2201 W m^{-2} , and -0.0533 W m^{-2} , respectively), indicating a net cooling effect. Notably, in the 80SW and 80PW scenarios, the ERF estimates had error bars that extended across both positive and negative values, highlighting substantial uncertainty.

Beyond direct aerosol-radiation interactions, the role of aerosols as CCN influences the ERF patterns (Figure 8). The 80EB SSB scenario resulted in the strongest cooling effect over Finland, as the increase in BC and OC emissions enhanced CCN availability. This led to an increase in CDNC, brightening clouds through the Twomey effect and increasing solar radiation reflection. The 80EB LSB scenario exhibited a

Figure 8: Effect of alternate wood use scenarios on ERF of anthropogenic forest-based aerosols in Finland. Figure adapted from **Paper II**.

weaker cooling effect, reflecting the reduced CCN availability due to lower BC and OC emissions. Similarly, the 80SW scenario showed a moderate cooling effect, primarily attributed to increased sulfate aerosol concentrations, which enhanced cloud reflectivity. In contrast, the 80PW scenario demonstrated a net warming effect across most of Finland. This was driven largely by the significant reduction in SO_2 emissions, which weakened sulfate-induced cloud brightening. The decrease in sulfate aerosols led to lower CDNC, reducing the ability of clouds to reflect incoming solar radiation, thus shifting the radiative balance toward warming. The smaller reductions in BC and OC emissions in this scenario did not provide sufficient compensatory cooling to offset the loss of sulfate-driven cooling.

4.3 Cloud Microphysical Responses to Aerosol Perturbations

We investigated the microphysical relationship between CCN and CDNC to improve our understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions, as detailed in **Paper III**. To do so, we applied traditional regression methods, such as OLS in its two-dimensional form and BLS regression methods to satellite observations and climate model data. We primarily used satellite data from MODIS to derive CCN and CDNC, and complemented this analysis with simulations from the aerosol-climate model ECHAM-HAMMOZ. In ECHAM-HAMMOZ, we use N_{100} , which is the sum of all aerosol particles with

diameters larger than 100 nm, as proxy for the CCN concentration, while CDNC is calculated explicitly. Our analysis focused primarily on the stratocumulus clouds over the Northern Pacific Ocean as explained in **Paper III**.

Although satellites provide several advantages for studying aerosol-cloud interactions on a global scale, a significant limitation is that analyses using satellite retrievals to estimate CCN-CDNC relationships are typically restricted to cloud top measurements of CDNC. Meanwhile, the CCN values represent the atmospheric column-integrated burdens from cloud-free regions adjacent to the cloud fields. However, in reality, CCN influence CDNC at the cloud base, where cloud droplets are formed. This discrepancy between where CCN are measured and where they have their actual impact can introduce uncertainties into the analysis of CCN-CDNC relationship, potentially affecting our understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions.

In **Paper III**, we explore the limitations of this approach, primarily by testing the skills of different regression techniques to account for different kinds of uncertainties. To improve the consistency and reliability of our results, we integrate satellite-retrieved CCN-CDNC data with climate model-simulated CCN column burdens and CDNC at cloud top. Additionally, we incorporated aerosol index, a widely used CCN proxy from satellite, to further support our findings.

We compared the ability of OLS and BLS regression methods in capturing the relationship between CCN and CDNC in both satellite and climate model data. The results demonstrated that OLS regression did not visually capture the relationship between CCN and CDNC in either satellite observations or climate model simulations (Figures 9(a) and 9(b)). OLS has inherent limitations as it does not account for errors in both the x and y axes, leading to biased slope estimates (Mikkonen et al., 2019). In contrast, BLS regression visually provided a better fit to the data, with a regression line more closely matching the observed CCN-CDNC data-points. However, BLS consistently yielded slopes greater than 1 for both satellite and climate model datasets.

A slope greater than 1 is unphysical, as it implies that a small increase in CCN leads to a disproportionately large increase in CDNC, which contradicts the expected behaviour of cloud droplet formation. However, It should be noted that we used N_{100} as a proxy for CCN concentrations. In certain supersaturation conditions, smaller aerosol particles (with diameters smaller than 100 nm) can also contribute to CCN activation, which leads to actual CCN concentrations that exceed N_{100} (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016).

Figure 9: Susceptibility of (a) cloud-top CDNC to changes in CCN from satellite observations and (b) cloud-top CDNC to changes in CCN from climate model simulation, using BLS and OLS regression methods, with colors representing the number of data points. Figure adopted from **Paper III**.

While this may partially explain the observed slopes greater than 1, it is crucial to note that slopes significantly greater than 1 remain unphysical, as they imply an unrealistic increase in CDNC relative to CCN. This suggests that additional factors, such as meteorological conditions, aerosol composition, or measurement uncertainties, are influencing the CCN-CDNC relationship. Furthermore, these larger-than-one slopes could be indicative of Simpson’s paradox, where the aggregated relationship between CCN and CDNC differs from underlying group-specific trends due to confounding influences (Boser, 2024; Simpson, 1951).

We continued the analysis to identify the key factors driving CDNC variability and the key parameters contributing to the high CCN-CDNC slopes estimated by BLS. To this end, we employed a machine learning-based feature selection approach using random forest (RF) regression. We first evaluated the RF model’s ability to predict CDNC using satellite-derived and climate model parameters. Figures 10(a) and 10(b) demonstrate that the RF model effectively predicts CDNC, achieving an R^2 of 0.82 for satellite data and 0.62 for climate model data. These results provide confidence in the model’s capability to capture the relationships between CDNC and its governing factors. Feature importance analysis using RF regression was conducted separately for satellite

Figure 10: (a) Satellite derived CDNC against RF predicted CDNC, (b) Modelled CDNC against RF predicted CDNC, with colors representing the number of data points. (c) Normalized feature importance scores for satellite-based observations. (d) Normalized feature importance scores for climate model data. Error bars in (c) and (d) represent the standard deviation of the feature importance distribution across all trees in the forest. Figure adopted from **Paper III**.

and model datasets to ensure consistency in identifying key drivers of CDNC variability. Figures 10(c) and 10(d) display the normalized feature importance scores for both datasets, revealing a remarkable similarity in the primary factors influencing CDNC. Across both satellite and model data, the three most critical variables were LWP, CCN burden, and updraft velocity. To validate these findings, we performed additional interpretability analyses using SHAP values and permutation feature importance, both of which reinforced that CCN, LWP, and updraft velocity are the dominant controls on CDNC variability. This consistency underscores the importance of considering updraft variability alongside CCN concentrations when analyzing aerosol-cloud interactions.

Figure 11: Variability of mean updraft velocity with cloud-top CDNC as a function of CCN burden in (a) satellite and (b) climate model data. Note different scales for updraft velocity. Markings in (a) are CDNC simulated by cloud parcel model for different updraft velocities. Figure adopted from **Paper III**.

Given the strong role of updraft velocity in aerosol activation, we further explored its influence on CDNC variability using both observed and modelled datasets. Figure 11 presents the CDNC-CCN relationship coloured by updraft velocity for both MODIS retrievals and climate model data. The updrafts derived from the satellite data and the climate model updrafts generally agree well. However, despite this general agreement, we observed systematic differences in updraft magnitudes, with the climate model typically simulating higher updraft velocities than those derived from the satellite. This discrepancy likely reflects issues in the calculation of model updrafts.

Importantly, our analysis suggests that the variability in updraft velocity contributes significantly to the spread observed in the CCN-CDNC relationship. The tendency of BLS regression to overestimate the slope may stem from its inability to account for this variability. Since updraft velocity exerts a fundamental control on droplet activation, failing to include it in regression analyses leads to an oversimplified representation of aerosol-cloud interactions. These results emphasize the need to consider these confounding factors when interpreting susceptibility relationships between aerosols and clouds.

Due to this observed variability in updraft velocity, clouds with different structures

inevitably mix, affecting their overall properties. One such key variable affected by the mixing of different clouds is the liquid water path (LWP). We analyzed LWP variations as a function of CDNC and CCN using both satellite and climate model data. The satellite observations revealed a negative correlation between CDNC and LWP, where higher CDNC values were associated with reduced LWP. This pattern aligns with previous studies suggesting that retrieval errors in satellite-derived CER may contribute to the observed LWP suppression at higher CDNC values (Arola et al., 2022; Kokkola et al., 2025). Conversely, climate model simulations exhibited a more complex LWP response to CDNC. At low CCN and CDNC levels, LWP was relatively high, suggesting that clouds with fewer droplets retained more liquid water. However, in regions of moderate to high CDNC, LWP tended to increase with increasing CCN concentration. This behaviour could be linked to large-scale meteorological patterns and CCN transport from source regions, as well as differences in wet scavenging efficiency in cloud processes, as shown in the supporting information in **Paper III**.

Figure 12: Susceptibility of cloud-top CDNC to changes in CCN burden from a) satellite observations and (b) climate model data using Elastic Net Regression. Markings in (a) are CDNC simulated by cloud parcel model for different updraft velocities Figure adopted from **Paper III**.

Due to this complexity in aerosol-cloud interactions and the limitations of conventional regression methods in isolating CCN effects on CDNC, we employed elastic net regression (ENR) as an alternative approach. ENR combines lasso and ridge regularization techniques, effectively mitigating issues related to multicollinearity and over-fitting.

Figure 12 presents the susceptibility of CDNC to CCN using ENR for both satellite and model datasets. The results demonstrate that ENR produces significantly lower and more physically consistent slopes compared to BLS.

Importantly, the results demonstrated that the slope estimates obtained using ENR were significantly lower than those derived from BLS, yielding values that were physically plausible and consistent with cloud parcel model simulations. Unlike BLS, which overestimated the sensitivity of CDNC to CCN perturbations, ENR captured a more realistic aerosol-cloud interaction by incorporating the role of updraft velocity and other relevant features. This was further validated using our test using synthetic dataset, where ENR successfully captured the prescribed slope while BLS showed notable deviations, as shown in the supporting information in **Paper III**. The findings from **Paper III** suggest that ENR provides a more accurate representation of the CCN-CDNC relationship, increasing confidence in its ability to more reliably estimate the slope between CCN and CDNC.

5 Review of papers and the author’s contribution

Paper I. This study investigates the impact of uncertainties in the volatility distribution of SOA on CCN concentrations and radiative forcing using the global aerosol-climate model ECHAM-SALSA. A nine-bin VBS was implemented to assess how different volatility assumptions influence SOA burden, CCN concentrations, and radiative effects. The results indicate that higher-volatility assumptions reduce SOA formation, leading to lower CCN concentrations and weaker cooling effects, while lower-volatility assumptions enhance SOA mass and increase CCN availability. A comparison between a three-bin and nine-bin VBS setup highlights that simplified VBS representations introduce biases in modelled SOA distributions and radiative forcing. For this study, I developed and implemented the VBS framework with extended bins in the global aerosol-climate model ECHAM-HAMMOZ. I conducted all global model simulations, performed comprehensive data analysis, generated all figures, interpreted the results, and wrote the manuscript in collaboration with co-authors.

Paper II. This study examines how changes in aerosol emissions from different forest biomass utilization scenarios affect radiative forcing over Finland. Different emission pathways were analyzed, focusing on variations in BC, OC, and SO₂ emissions. Model simulations revealed that scenarios with increased BC and OC emissions lead to a warming effect, whereas reductions in SO₂ emissions weaken the sulfate-driven cooling effect. Conversely, scenarios with increased SO₂ emissions resulted in enhanced sulfate aerosol formation, contributing to stronger cooling effects. For this study, I conducted all global aerosol-climate model simulations, performed comprehensive data analysis, generated all figures, interpreted the results, and contributed substantially to the manuscript writing.

Paper III. This study evaluates the challenges of estimating the susceptibility of CDNC to CCN perturbations using different regression techniques. Traditional regression methods such as two-dimensional OLS and BLS were found to be inadequate to estimate the CCN-CDNC relationship due to their inherent limitations. Both regression methods tend to produce biased slope estimates by not accounting for factors beyond CCN, such as updraft velocity and cloud dynamics. We employed RF model to isolate the effect of individual factors affecting CDNC variability and concluded that updraft velocity, CCN, and LWP play a crucial role. We suggest ENR as an alternative method for extracting the CCN-CDNC relationship. ENR is a reg-

ularization technique that combines the strengths of both lasso and ridge regression, allowing it to handle multicollinearity and improve model performance when predicting complex relationships like CCN and CDNC. The results demonstrate that ENR produces physically plausible slopes, consistent with cloud parcel model simulations, and better represents the aerosol-cloud interaction process. For this study, I conceptualized the research in collaboration with co-authors, conducted model simulations including the cloud parcel model and radiative transfer model, analyzed all model outputs and satellite observations, estimated satellite-derived updraft velocity, designed and implemented machine learning methods, interpreted the results, and wrote the manuscript with input from co-authors.

6 Conclusions

Aerosol-cloud interactions and SOA formation remain critical yet highly uncertain components of climate science. This dissertation contributes to advancing our understanding of these processes through three distinct yet interconnected studies focusing on (1) the sensitivity of SOA formation and radiative forcing to the volatility distribution of organic vapours, (2) the impact of forest biomass use scenarios on aerosol emissions and radiative effects, and (3) the challenges and improvements in estimating the relationship between CCN and CDNC using regression and machine learning methods. By integrating global climate modelling, observational data, and machine learning techniques, these studies provide novel understandings into how aerosol processes influence cloud properties, radiative forcing, and climate.

Paper I investigated how uncertainties in the volatility distribution of organic vapours influence SOA mass, CCN concentrations, and radiative forcing primarily utilizing a global aerosol-climate model. Using the sectional aerosol model SALSA within the ECHAM-HAMMOZ framework, we implemented a detailed nine-bin VBS representation for monoterpene oxidation products. Our results demonstrated that a reasonable perturbation in the assumed volatility distribution of semi-volatile organics significantly affect SOA formation and subsequent aerosol-cloud interactions. By shifting the volatilities of SOA precursors by one order of magnitude, we observed changes of up to $\pm 13\%$ in SOA mass burden over boreal regions. These changes directly influenced CCN concentrations and CDNC, albeit with a smaller relative effect. The largest changes in gas-particle partitioning occurred for the semi-volatile bins in the VBS, highlighting the importance of accurately constraining these volatilities to improve SOA predictions. Radiative forcing estimates further underscored the climate implications of volatility assumptions. A 10-fold decrease in SOA precursor volatility resulted in an ERF of -0.4 W m^{-2} , while a 10-fold increase led to an ERF of $+0.35 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. These results highlight the role of SOA in modulating aerosol-radiation and aerosol-cloud interactions, emphasizing that uncertainties in volatility distributions can lead to substantial differences in radiative effects. Additionally, we compared a three-bin VBS setup, commonly used in many global models due to computational constraints, against the more detailed nine-bin VBS setup. Our findings revealed that using fewer volatility bins led to a 20% lower SOA burden and a 10% increase in CCN concentrations, which in turn affected cloud properties and radiative forcing. This highlights

the importance of selecting an appropriate volatility bin resolution in climate models, as oversimplifications can introduce biases in aerosol-cloud interaction studies. While previous studies have focused primarily on ELVOCs (Barsanti et al., 2017; Ehn et al., 2014; Jokinen et al., 2015; Patoulias & Pandis, 2022; Shrivastava et al., 2024), the role of SVOCs in SOA formation may have been overlooked. Given that SVOCs contribute significantly to gas-particle partitioning, future research should refine volatility bin representations to improve their accuracy. Optimizing volatility frameworks will help balance computational efficiency with scientific accuracy, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of aerosol-climate interactions.

Paper II focused on evaluating how different scenarios of increased forest biomass use in Finland affect aerosol emissions and radiative forcing. By incorporating projected emissions from industrial and energy sectors into a global aerosol-climate model, we assessed the resulting changes in BC, OC, and SO₂ emissions, and their subsequent influence on radiative forcing. Our results showed distinct differences in aerosol emissions across four different biomass use scenarios. The 80SW scenario led to slightly higher BC and OC emissions but a significant increase in SO₂ emissions, promoting sulfate aerosol formation and resulting in a slight cooling effect ($-0.0061 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ IRF}_{ARI}$ and $-0.0533 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ ERF}$). In contrast, the 80PW scenario, which involved allocating the increased harvest to pulpwood production, led to substantial reductions in all three aerosol components, particularly SO₂, causing a net warming effect due to the diminished sulfate-driven cooling. The 80EB SSB and 80EB LSB scenarios, which involved enhanced bioenergy use with small-scale and large-scale burning, exhibited different radiative effects. While 80EB SSB led to a slight warming due to increased BC emissions ($+0.007 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ IRF}_{ARI}$), the 80EB LSB scenario resulted in a cooling effect ($-0.013 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ IRF}_{ARI}$), as reductions in BC and OC emissions outweighed the decreased sulfate burden. Examining the ERF, which accounts for both direct aerosol effects and aerosol-cloud interactions, revealed more pronounced climate impacts. The 80PW scenario had a strong warming effect ($+0.1338 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ ERF}$), primarily due to reduced sulfate-driven cloud brightening. Conversely, the 80EB SSB and 80EB LSB scenarios exhibited net cooling effects (-0.9725 W m^{-2} and $-0.2201 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ ERF}$, respectively), as increased aerosol emissions enhanced cloud albedo through the Twomey effect. These findings highlight the complex climate trade-offs associated with different biomass use strategies. While reductions in wood combustion may lower carbonaceous aerosol emissions, the concurrent decrease in sulfate aerosols can lead to unintended warming effects. This underscores the need for holistic policy assessments that consider

both emissions from wood use and their climate impacts when evaluating bioenergy strategies.

Paper III addressed one of the longstanding challenges in aerosol-cloud interaction research: accurately quantifying the sensitivity of CDNC to changes in CCN. Traditional regression methods, particularly OLS and BLS, have been widely used for this purpose, but are limited by inherent methodological limitations. OLS in its two-dimensional form tends to produce biased CCN-CDNC slope estimate due to its inability to account for measurement errors in both x and y axes. BLS, while providing a better fit visually, produces slope greater than 1, suggesting an unphysical relationship between CCN and CDNC. These biases stem from the influence of additional meteorological factors, particularly updraft velocity, which affects cloud droplet activation. To address these limitations, we employed RF regression for feature selection and ENR for slope estimation. RF analysis identified updraft velocity, CCN burden, and LWP as the most critical factors influencing CDNC variability, highlighting the need to consider meteorological dependencies when analyzing aerosol-cloud interactions. Updraft velocity affects the water vapour supersaturation at cloud base, which in-turn influences cloud droplet activation. Since variability in updrafts leads to fluctuations in cloud formation conditions, we are bound to mix clouds with different structures and phases, which further affects cloud dynamics such as LWP. As a solution to better disentangle the sole effect of aerosols from CDNC, we propose the use of ENR as an alternative regression technique. ENR, which integrates lasso and ridge regularization to reduce multicollinearity and over-fitting, provided physically consistent slope estimates. Unlike BLS, which inflated the CCN-CDNC slope, ENR produced slopes below 1, aligning closely with cloud parcel model simulations based on fundamental droplet activation physics. This result suggests that machine learning approaches offer significant improvements over traditional regression techniques in estimating aerosol-cloud susceptibilities.

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